

THE USE OF MODERN INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND ITS EFFECTIVENESS

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Abstract. *This article is about how to use the methods of modern teaching of innovative technologies so that they become the leading aspect of learning a foreign language, and fully contribute to the formation and consolidation of the study of the material. Naturally, the question of how to organize the work on the assimilation of grammatical structures in English lessons cannot be separated from other aspects of integrated learning: lexico-semantic, orthoepic, orthographic work, from work on the formation of communicative skills in all forms.*

Keywords: *methods, teaching, motivation, foreign language, meaning, textbook, teacher.*

After the independence of our country, the interest in teaching foreign languages has grown and many opportunities have been created for young people and different modern technologies have entered our life. In today's fast-paced world, science and technology are also growing rapidly. Development in every field is moving forward.

In particular, great changes are taking place in science. Delivery of each subject to students using new innovative pedagogical technologies is one of the main requirements of today's education. The effective use of Innovative technologies, such as computers, the Internet, multimedia resources in the educational process is the only way to show the quality of education. One of the innovative technologies of improving the students' communicative abilities is using multimedia in the process of teaching and learning in the classroom. Proper use of multimedia in classroom will provide the opportunity for interacting with diverse texts that give students a solid background in the tasks and content of mainstream courses. Furthermore, because educational technology is expected to become an integral part of the curriculum, students must become proficient in accessing and using electronic resources Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, reading, listening comprehension, and speaking), each of which provides specific concepts and skills.

Educational technology is the effective use of modern information technology in the educational process. It also aims to improve the quality and effectiveness of education through the introduction of modern innovative technologies in the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages to using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is invaluable. The use of technology is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening and speaking). For example, to listen and understand, of course, it is impossible to do this process without a computer, player, CDs. Listening is one of the most important parts of language learning. This requires the student to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, grammatical rules, vocabulary, and meanings at the same time. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in education is the ability of students to know and use information and communication technologies.

Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technology is one of the most effective ways. In this process we should include:

- When using computers, the student can watch and listen to videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons in a foreign language
- You can listen and watch radio broadcasts in foreign languages and TV programs
- the use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are more traditional methods

The use of these tools will make the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students. In the process of globalization it is hard to imagine our lives without the internet. It is one of the most effective ways to learn and teach a foreign language.

You will be able to communicate with foreign speakers through the Internet. Writing exercises can be improved by writing a letter via e-mail. The most important issue is the introduction of modern communication technologies in the educational process, their targeted and correct, effective use, through which the student's interest in a foreign language, to increase the effectiveness of teaching. This will create opportunities for the use of innovative educational technologies and increase demand.

The basis of the use of game technology is the activity that activates and accelerates the student. According to psychologists, the psychological mechanisms of playful activity are based on the fundamental needs of the individual to express themselves, to find a stable place in life, to self-manage, to realize their potential. At the heart of any game should be the generally accepted principles and tactics of education. Learning games should be based on the subjects. During the games, the student is more interested in this activity than in a normal lesson and works more comfortably. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a way of teaching.

Students are interested in playful lessons, they strive to win, and the teacher uses them to educate the student. The student is interested in believing that he or she can play, speak, listen, understand, and write in English.

We know that in the current educational process, the student must be a subject.

Focusing on more interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English lessons is to teach students to think independently. Today, English teachers use the following innovative methods based on the experience of teachers in the United States and the United Kingdom:

Creative Problem Solving- To use this method, the beginning of the story is read and the conclusion is left to the judgment of the students. Merry Riddles

- Merry Riddles is an important part of teaching English to students, as they learn words they are unfamiliar with and find the answer to a riddle;
- Quick answers help to increase the effectiveness of the lesson;
- —Warm-up exercises to use various games in the classroom to engage students in the lesson ;
- "Pantomime" is a method that can be used in a lesson where very difficult topics need to be explained, or when students are tired of writing exercises;
- A chain story method helps to develop students' oral skills
- Acting characters This method can be used in all types of lessons.

Professionals such as Interpreter, Translator, Writer, and Poet can participate in the class and talk to students

- The —When pictures speak method is more convenient and helps to teach English, to develop students' oral speech, it is necessary to use thematic pictures.

As we have seen, each innovative technology has its own set of advantages. All of these methods involve collaboration between teacher and student, active participation of the student in the educational process. In short, the use of innovative methods in English lessons develops students' logical thinking skills, fluency, and the ability to respond quickly and accurately. Such methods stimulate the student's desire for knowledge. The student strives to prepare well for the lessons. This makes students active participants in the learning process. As the education system sets itself the task of nurturing a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future we will contribute to the further development of effective ways for future teachers to effectively use innovative technologies.

Many are looking for ways that would help improve the effectiveness of raining. Teachers always excites the actual problem is to make sure that all the students were interested in a lesson to all involved in the learning process, so that there are no indifferent. How to use stories to develop the personality of the student, his creative thinking, the ability to analyze the past and present, to make their own conclusions and to have their own point of view? All these tasks can be implemented under conditions of vigorous activity of students using interactive methods and teacher training methods. As language teachers, we have a tradition of integrating new media into our teaching. We have embraced any new technology, which was likely to improve learning. Mindful of the need to bring native speaker voices into the classroom, teachers in the first half of the 20th century took gramophones into their classrooms. These were replaced by reel-to-reel tape recorders when the price was right and appropriate recordings became available. Brave souls acquired microphones and encouraged students to record their own voices, to accustom them to hearing themselves speaking in another language. The next innovation was the language laboratory, coming as it did at a time when the audio-lingual method was to the fore and drills were considered central to successful language learning. Those entrusted with the maintenance of language laboratories heaved a sigh of relief when audiocassette recorders replaced reel-to-reel tape. Slide and filmstrip projectors, film projectors and television sets also found their way into language classrooms, followed by video players and video cameras. All of these innovations made their entrance as "bolt-ons". It was only when their characteristics were fully understood and their strengths identified in comparison with existing media that they become integrated into the delivery strategy of the teachers concerned, and into published courses. The innovative technologies that we reviewed today significantly enrich and diversify the teaching of foreign languages. In place of the monotonous work comes intelligent creative search, during which formed a new type of personality, active and purposeful, focused on constant self-education and development.

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